

INCIDENCE OF RAPE IN PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION ROUTES: A STUDY OF TRICYCLE (KEKE) RIDERS IN UYO METROPOLIS, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Okoro Sunday Asangausung, Mercy Emmanuel Samuel & Mfon Effiong Asuquo

Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Uyo, Uyo
Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

How to cite this article: Asangausung, O. S., Samuel, M. E. & Asuquo, M. E. (2020). Incidence of rape in public transportation routes: a study of tricycle (keke) riders in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *South South Journal of Culture and Development*, 22(1&2), 82-118.

Summary

The study investigated the role played by tricycle (Keke) riders in the incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It was guided by the assumptions of the Routine Activity Theory of Lawrence Cohen and Marcus Felson in 1979. Survey design method was adopted in the study. A sample size of 400 was selected from the constituent parts of Uyo metropolis consisting Uyo, Ibesikpo Asutan, Uruan, Ibiono Ibom, Itu, Nsit Ibom and Etinan Local Government Areas using proportional stratified sample equation. Multi-stage sampling technique (cluster, convenience and snowball) was employed. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaire and in-depth interview guide to seek opinion of the respondents. The questionnaire structured in Yes or No options, Strongly Disagreed (SD), Disagreed (D), Undecided (U), Agreed (A) and Strongly Agreed (SA) format. Four Hundred (400) copies of questionnaire were circulated and Three Hundred and Ninety-Seven (397) copies were retrieved from respondents and same were used for presentation. Quantitative data were presented descriptively using

frequency tables and simple percentages. Conversational analysis approach was adopted for analysis of qualitative data. Findings among others show that rape is alarming mostly in the transportation routes across the constituent parts of Uyo Metropolis. Tricycles are not only used for public transportation within Uyo Metropolis, but they are also notorious for being used for criminal activities including rape. Tricycle riders have been a great danger to the lives of their passengers and residents. The study recommends among other things, that passengers should be security conscious at all times mostly when boarding commercial tricycles. Online booking tricycles like Opay and many others should be patronized since they are safe and secured for passengers and their luggage. It is an advocacy that all tricycles in Uyo Metropolis should be prohibited from using side tarpaulins. The entrance doors of the tricycles should be open to the public to see what is inside. This is because most atrocities are committed when the side tarpaulins are covered. Victims of rape should be sympathized and not stigmatised against. The law enforcement agents must do more than arresting the culprits; they must be made to face the full weight of the law.

Introduction

Across most cities in Africa and Nigeria in particular, conspicuous sights of commercial tricycles popularly known as “Keke NAPEP” abound. Tricycle as a means of public transportation was first introduced into the city of Lagos by the military administration of Brigadier General Mohammed Buba Marwa (Rtd) between 1996 to 1999. It was a poverty alleviation gesture on the part of government since many jobless youths and other individuals were expected to benefit from it through ownership at subsidized rates (Akpor, 2009). In Lagos state,

tricycles are popularly known as “Keke Marwa” (Idialu, 2016). In 2001, a former President of Nigeria, Chief Olusegun Obasanjo formed National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) distributed Keke NAPEP to different parts of Nigeria as a means of poverty intervention and a strategy to convert area boys from being idle to a productive work force (Mgbemena, 2013).

Tricycle is an Asian innovation (Doyo, 2012) and it has form an important part of the intra-city transport system, following the ban placed on motorcycles (Balami and Garba, 2019) in some states in Nigeria. There has been an alarming increase in reports of rape cases across the country. We have read of some horrific accounts of this heinous crime through various media channels in recent times. Tricycle drivers know the layout of their small communities and many of the people who live there. They have been eyewitnesses to crimes. They have themselves been perpetrators of heinous crimes, rape included (Doyo, 2012). Crime associated with tricycles as a means of public transportation has become a recurrent decimal, resulting to series of criminal activities including rape, robbery, pick-pocketing, cultism,

fraud, murder, and other notorious crimes orchestrated by bad elements in the system. No wonder Doyo (2012) pointed out that tricycles do not commit crime; it is their drivers and riders who have sometimes been involved in gruesome crimes with the aid of these three-wheeled vehicles. Onuegbu (2019) reported that Akwa Ibom State Government has received over 180 cases and prosecuted over 18 culprits for cases of defilement and rape since 2018.

The implication of crimes associated with tricycle riders are seen in increased government spending of public funds to provide security. There is fear among residents and passengers. Residents have become more withdrawn and defensive. Some streets have adopted neighbourhood night watch strategy to revitalize their communities from decay.

To the best of my knowledge, no studies have been conducted on the activities of Keke riders towards the prevalence of rape in Nigeria. However, Balami and Garba (2019) conducted a study in Maiduguri, Borno State to determine the prevalence of road accidents, near-misses, and their associated factors among commercial tricycle drivers. Also,

Oladipo (2012), Umaru (2013), Onifade, Aduradola and Amao (2012), Yakubu (2012) and Idialu (2016) had focused on the contributions of commercial tricycles to economic and national development in Nigeria.

The objective of this study was to examine the incidence of rape in public transportation with much emphasis to the role of Keke riders in Uyo Metropolis. With the prevailing paradigm shift of focus from commercial motorcycle base transportation to a more organized city transportation system, an effort to investigate crimes associated with a very important means of commercial transport (tricycles) on our streets become necessary. The results of this study would objectively reveal the role played by Keke riders in the incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis. This would guide the development of evidence-based crime prevention strategies which would further improve the present observed trend.

Review of Related Literature

Rape is a crime, a pandemic of monumental consequences and rape is defined as the unlawful intercourse; called forcible rape if committed against the will of the victim by the use of threats or force (Reid, 1982 cited in Iwarimie-Jaja, 2012). This definition captures the meaning given

to rape in common law, where rape is defined “as the carnal knowledge of a female forcibly and against her will” (Green, 1978 cited in Iwarimie-Jaja, 2012:266). The rape act could be initiated by persons who maintain pre-established role relationships (e.g. neighbours, co-workers, husband’s best friends, relatives, friends and present or former boyfriends) (Iwarimie-Jaja, 2012). Galadima (No date) further pointed out that the most important component of rape is that a person commits the offence when he has carnal knowledge of; (a) a female forcibly and against her will (b) a female who is less than ten years of age. Carnal knowledge in rape occurs when there is any penetration of the female sex organ by the male sex organ. In this case, rape could be committed by a Keke rider against his female passengers.

The Criminal Code Act, 2004

The Criminal Code Act (Criminal Code) (2004) is applicable in the southern states of the country. Each of the states has its Criminal Code.

Section 357 of the Criminal Code Act defines rape this way:

“Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl, without her consent or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of threats or intimidation of any kind, or by fear of

harm, or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act or in the case of a married woman, by personating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called rape” (Section 357 of the Criminal Code Act, 2004).

An attempt to commit rape is also an offence under the Criminal Code and it is a felony, punishable with imprisonment for fourteen years, with or without caning. Section 358 of the Criminal Code provides imprisonment for life, with or without caning as punishment for rape. It is worthy to note that from the definition of rape in section 357 of the Criminal Code does not recognize men or boys as victims of rape. The Criminal Code does not also recognize marital rape. The provisions of the Criminal Code indicate that rape can only be committed by persons of the male gender.

The Penal Code Act, 1990

The Penal Code Act (Penal Code) (1990) is applicable in the Northern states of Nigeria. Section 282 of the Penal Code provides that Rape is said to occur where a man has sexual intercourse with a woman in any of the following circumstances:

“(a) against her will, (b) without her consent, (c) with her consent, when her consent has been obtained by putting her in fear of death or hurt, (d) With her consent when the man knows that he is not her husband and that her consent is given because she believes that he is another man to whom she is or believes herself to be lawfully married, (e) With or without her consent, when she is under fourteen years of age or of unsound mind”.

The punishment for rape is fourteen years. The Penal Code does not recognize men or boys as victims of rape. It also does not recognize

marital rape where the woman has attained the age of puberty and it is specifically stated in Section 282 (2). The provisions of the Penal Code indicate that rape can only be committed by persons of the male gender. Section 283 of the Penal Code provides imprisonment for life or for any less term and or a fine punishment for rape.

Child Rights Act, 2003

The Child Rights Act (CRA) (2003) is a Federal Law which was enacted to protect the rights of children. It has been domesticated in a number of states in Nigeria. Section 31 (1) & (2) of the CRA provides that:

“any person who shall have sexual intercourse with a child commits an offence of rape and is liable on conviction to imprisonment for life; it is immaterial that: (a) the offender believed the person to be of or above the age of eighteen years; or (b) the sexual intercourse was with the consent of the child”. The CRA does not restrict victims of rape to the female gender. It also recognizes that the offence of rape could be committed either by a man or woman.

Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Act, 2015

The Violence Against Persons (Prohibition Act) (VAPP) (2015) prohibits all forms of violence against people in private and public life.

It is applicable in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Section 1 (1) of the VAPP provides that a person commits the offence of rape if:

“(a) He or she intentionally penetrates the vagina, anus, or mouth of another person with any other part of his body or anything else; (b) The other person does not consent to the penetration; or (c) The consent is obtained by force or means of threat or intimidation of any kind or by fear of harm or by means of false or fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act or the use of any substance or additive capable of taking away the will of such person or in the case of a married person by impersonating his or her spouse”.

Section 1(2) provides life imprisonment as punishment for the offence. Where the offender is less than 14 years, the punishment is a maximum term of 14 years imprisonment. In other cases, a minimum of 12 years imprisonment is provided by the Act and for gang rape, the offenders are liable jointly to a minimum term of 20 years without an option of fine. The Act also recommends the award of appropriate compensation to the victim by the court. Section 1(4) VAPP mandates that a register of sexual offenders should be maintained and accessible to the Public.

The provisions of VAPP with regards to rape are quite wide as it did not like other laws restrict its definition of rape to protect only females in relation to vaginal penetration. VAPP does not restrict

victims of rape to the female gender. The VAPP recognizes that sex goes beyond the use of the primary sexual organs and extends the scope to anus and mouth. It has been observed that before in Nigeria it was difficult to bring forceful anal or oral sex under the umbrella of rape as such was not part of our laws. The VAPP also indicates that penetration here need not only by the sex organ (penis) of the offender but by any part of his body or anything else. The Act, despite its laudable provisions has been criticized for not stipulating a minimum amount as compensation for rape so as well as the punishment prescribed for gang rape.

The question one may now ask is how effective the laws which pertain to rape have been over the years in securing convictions and serving as deterrents to offenders. It has been observed that prosecuting rape cases can be quite tough due to a myriad of factors ranging from stigma to the provisions of the law itself on the issue. Furthermore, information obtained from the International Centre for Investigative Reporting (ICIR) website indicates that there have been 65 rape convictions between 1973 and 2019 in Nigeria. This number, no doubt is

insignificant considering the number of reported cases of rape in the country. There is a need for amendment of the laws on rape.

The VAPP can be termed the most progressive piece of legislation on rape in Nigeria considering its far-reaching provisions on the subject matter. Its provisions are quite laudable and there is an urgent need to amend the other laws touching on rape to mirror its provisions on the subject matter. States should also enact laws similar to the VAPP. A database of sexual offenders ought to be maintained in every state in Nigeria. The databases should be easily accessible and regularly updated. Maintaining such a database may likely prove difficult but if the narrative must be changed in Nigeria, things need to be done differently. A mindset reset is required. The culture of blaming and stigmatizing rape victims should also be spoken against and stopped.

Incidence of Rape in Nigeria's Cities involving Keke Riders

In Uyo, Paradise Newspaper (2016) reported that suspected members of a three-man gang allegedly specialized in raping girls around Uyo metropolis were apprehended by a team of State Criminal Investigation Department (SCID) and Special Anti-Robbery Squad

(SARS), following a tip-off by one of their victims. According to the Police Public Relation Officer in Akwa Ibom State said, “the suspects went around Uyo Metropolis using a commercial tricycle (Keke Napep) to pick unsuspecting female passengers, hypnotized and raping them”. Police Public Relation Officer also added that “In their confession, while Etim and Essien pretended to be passengers in the tricycle, Archibong is the rider of the Keke Napep. The report was made by their last victim, an undergraduate of the University of Uyo. It was disclosed that while the victim boarded the tricycle, she was hypnotized and then taken to unknown destination where she was raped. Confessing to the crime, the suspects said they have lost count of women they have raped” (Paradise Newspaper, 2016).

Another scenario in Uyo, Odey (2019) reported that a 27 year old tricycle operator Mr. Edet Edem who hails from Oku Iboku in Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State was apprehended for allegedly defiling a 10-year-old girl (name withheld) in Uyo. It was gathered that the tricycle operator lives in Uyo and after committing the crime, took the girl to Use Offot market square and dumped her there in a pool of

blood and absconded. The girl was later rescued by a passerby, Mariam Daniels, who rushed victim to St. Luke's Hospital, Anua for medical treatment. Mariam Daniels, a member of a non-governmental organization (Journalists Alliance Against Gender-Based Violence) said:

“I was moved by the victim's pitiable state after noticing that the girl was lying helplessly in the market square. I took the girl to the suspect's residence and when I arrived there, I saw a pool of blood in the suspect's apartment. The suspect's door was locked and there was no indication that he was within the neighbourhood” (Odey, 2019).

In his statement at the Ewet Police Station, the suspect Mr. Edet Edem confessed that he committed the crime, that apart from being a tricycle operator, he is a senior official of a church. “Yes, I slept with her, but when I noticed that she was bleeding; I wiped the blood from the floor” (Odey, 2019).

In Lagos State, Scroll News (2016) reported that a 15-year-old Semisola Olona was allegedly raped by a commercial tricycle rider, known as Mr. Lati Ajoje. In tears, the victim, Olona, who claimed she was a virgin before the incident, narrated how Mr. Lati Ajoje took advantage of her:

“I was on my way to my mother's shop on January 15, 2016 and Mr. Lati Ajoje offered to me a drop to my mother's canteen. I did not suspect

anything. I even thanked him as he carried me with his Keke. When we got to the bus stop, he turned and faced another route. I asked him if he was not going to my mum's shop again. He didn't answer me. I told him to stop me at the bus stop but he refused. He then told me to be patient that he only wanted to go and collect something at Water Estate. I insisted he should drop me. He did not listen to me, he ignored me. He got to where he was going and he stopped at an uncompleted building and told me to get down. I asked him why? and he said he wanted to tell me something. I told him I didn't like the place he brought me and I was already feeling uncomfortable. He forced me into the uncompleted building. I was struggling. I even had to bite him but he didn't bulge. He removed my clothes. I told him he would rather kill me than doing anything to me. But he said he wasn't going to kill me but he would still have sex with me. That was how he forced himself on me and raped me. Ajoje threatened to kill me if I will ever tell anybody about the incident. After raping me, he used one rag to clean me up. He gave me N200 to pay my way and I told him I wasn't going to take his money. I was afraid to tell anybody because he had said he would kill me. But eventually, I had to tell my sister who told my mother. I have not seen him again since then. He is no longer coming to my mother's shop" (Scroll News, 2016).

In Lagos State, Okoli and Alaribe (2016) reported that on the 21th October, 2016, operatives of Rapid Response Squad (RRS) of Lagos State Police Command apprehended one Dada Azeez (male), 28 years old, a tricycle operator and Wasiu Agunbiade for allegedly abducting a 15-year old girl and turned her to a sex slave at Agege area of the state. The alleged abduction of the girl was disclosed by her sister, Mrs. Gbemisola, who disclosed that the girl was abducted with a sum of ₦58,

000 meant for her thrift contribution. Confessing to the crime, the suspect Dada Azeez said:

“We started having secret affair about a year ago, but her sister frowned at our relationship when she got to know. In order to be having regular conversation with her, I bought a mobile phone for her and instructed her to hide it from her sister. So, whenever she intended coming to meet me, she will call and I will describe our meeting point for her. I was able to perpetrate the crime when her sister sent her on errand on one Sunday afternoon. However, I didn't know she was with such amount of money. I just wanted to take her far away from her guardian for not supporting our relationship” (Okoli and Alaribe, 2016)

The victim, Ibukun narrated her ordeal in the hands of the suspect thus:

“The suspect forcefully deflowered me. He forced himself on me the very first day I visited him at his residence. Since then, he has been having sex with me without wearing condom. He slept with me anywhere and even at his friends' place where he hid me for weeks. I succumbed to him because I could not go back home. He collected the ₦58, 000 my sister gave me. He fed me thrice a day probably from that thrift contribution money. Also, arrested along with the suspect, was one of his friends, Wasiu Agunbiade, Wasiu Agunbiade who aided the abduction by accommodating the suspect and the teenager in his one-room apartment in Agege” (Okoli and Alaribe, 2016).

Wasiu Agunbiade, an accomplice in his regrets confessed thus:

“I only accommodated them for a night. I never knew he abducted the little girl. If I had known the girl was abducted, I would have advised him to return her to her parents. I never believed he could commit such crime. He begged me to accommodate them for one night with her in my room. He left my place the following day to somewhere else. I regretted allowing them to pass the night in my place” (Okoli and Alaribe, 2016).

Again, in Lagos State, Jeremiah (2015) reported that a tricycle operator, Obinna Ezechukwu, 31 years old, has been arraigned before an Ikeja Magistrates' Court for allegedly raping a lady. The suspect was charged for false pretence, stealing and rape. The prosecutor, Inspector Rachael Williams, told the court that:

“The offences were committed on July 9, 2015 at the residence of the accused; that the accused who picked the victim every day from the bus stop to her place of work, promised to get her an apartment. After the accused had collected ₦30, 000 under the pretence of securing one of the vacant rooms in his compound for the victim, he invited her to meet the landlord. On getting to the home of the accused, he offered her a drink and that was how she slept off and when she woke up, she found herself that she had been raped. She told the court the victim was 23-years-old and that the offences contravened Sections 258(1), 285 and 312(a) of the Criminal Law of Lagos State. The accused pleaded not guilty. The Chief Magistrate, Tajudeen Elias, granted bail to the accused in the sum of N200, 000, with two sureties each in like sum” (Jeremiah, 2015).

Still, in Lagos, PM News (2018) reported that an Ikeja Chief Magistrates' Court ordered the remand of a tricycle operator Yusuf Raheem, 22 years old, for raping a 16-year-old girl. The Chief Magistrate, Mr P. E. Nwaka, ordered that Raheem, whose plea was not taken be remanded in Kirikiri Prisons pending advice from the State Director of Public Prosecutions (DPP). Earlier, the Police Prosecutor,

Christopher John told the court that the accused committed the offence on May 12, at No. 22, Tinar Street, Amukoko, Lagos. The accused accosted the girl on her way back from Church, lured her to an uncompleted building and raped her. The offence contravened Section 260 of the Criminal Law of Lagos State, 2015.

In Taraba State, Olonade (2018) reported that Mercy, a final year student of School of Nursing, Jalingo in Taraba State, was messily raped to death by three evil men in a Keke around Specialist and School of Nursing's Bridge. Mercy was raped, stabbed and later found swimming in her pool of blood before taken to the nearby specialist hospital where she later gave up the ghost in the morning of Tuesday June 5, 2018.

In Abuja, Isah (2019) reported that a 33-year-old Mr. Victor Achianu, a tricycle operator was arrested by the police for allegedly raping his passenger at Gidan Mangoro in Orozo, an Abuja suburb. The FCT Commissioner of Police, Bala Ciroma, who stated while briefing newsmen at the command headquarters in Abuja, said that 'the suspect took the victim from Jikwoyi en-route Gidan Daya in Orozo, and then he drove to a secluded spot at Gidan Mangoro and raped her. The tricycle

operator abandoned his tricycle and fled from the scene when the woman raised an alarm, which attracted the attention of some passers-by who came to her rescue. The suspect was immediately arrested and was identified by his victim as the person who raped her, after the conduct of an identification parade’.

The available literature derived from different media reports show that the involvement of Keke riders does not go unnoticed mostly in Nigeria’s major cities. Despite the fact that incidence of rape is not always reported to the Police by the victims, it is evidenced in the literature that cases of rape among tricycle riders are becoming worrisome. The offence of rape is heinous because apart from constituting an invasion of the most intimate privacy of the victim, it usually has devastating effects on victims and their families respectively. It constitutes a criminal offence both under Nigerian law and other jurisdictions. Findings of the study have been the effort of the researcher and have contributed to the body of knowledge.

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the assumptions of Routine Activity Theory (RAT) of Lawrence E. Cohen and Marcus Felson (Cohen and Felson, 1979). Unlike other criminological theories, routine activity theory studies crime as an event, closely relates crime to its environment and emphasize its ecological process, thereby diverting academic attention away from mere offenders. Routine activity theory is based on the assumption that crime can be committed by anyone who has the opportunity and victims could be anybody. Routine activities theory requires three elements be present for a crime to occur:

- (a) a motivated offender with criminal intentions
- (b) a suitable victim or target, and
- (c) the absence of a capable guardian who can prevent the crime from happening.

The premise of routine activity theory is that crime is relatively unaffected by social causes such as poverty, inequality, and unemployment. According to Cohen and Felson (1979), the reason for crime increase is that the prosperity of contemporary society offers more opportunities for crime to occur. For example, permission to use

tricycles in the city of Uyo makes it possible for criminals to move more freely to conduct their violations and on the other hand, provide more targets for them.

The applicability of routine activities theory to the study lies to the fact that the use of Keke for public transportation in Uyo Metropolis may encompass part of the routine activities of criminals (tricycle riders and their accomplice), suitable targets (passengers and residents.) and the absence of a capable guardian (the Law Enforcement Agents like the Police). This is particularly true when considering the whole journey approach to public transport using commercial tricycles from departure point to destination point. It is possible that the availability of commercial tricycles in the city and patronage by the public may actually influence a person's routine activities.

The analytic focus of the routine activity theory emphasizes on things that motivate tricycle riders to commit crime, the possibility of victims to be affected and lack of those vested with the responsibility to prevent crime occurrences. Routine activities theory relates the pattern of offending to the everyday patterns of social interaction.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The constituent parts of Uyo metropolis are Etinan, Ibesikpo Asutan, Ibiono Ibom, Itu, NsitIbom, Uruan and Uyo Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. Survey design that entails the use of both the quantitative and qualitative methods was adopted. The survey design enabled the researcher to collect data through structured questionnaire and in-depth interview from the sampled population without any manipulation. The primary data collected from the field were subjected to statistical presentation, analysis. The researcher relied heavily on the primary data. The population of this study comprises passengers, commuters, tricycle riders, tricycle union leaders, transport stakeholders and Police Officers in Uyo metropolis. Participants were from the age of 15 years and above drawn from the constituent parts of Uyo Metropolis. A sample size of 400 respondents was selected using the Taro Yamane's scientific formula. Also, proportionate stratification equation was used to determine the sample size for each stratum.

The respondents were selected using a multi-stage sampling technique which involved cluster, convenience and respondent driven sampling methods. Multi-stage sampling technique was necessary because the study requires a combination of sampling techniques to draw samples from the study population. The questionnaire had 40 items structured in Strongly Disagreed (SD), Disagreed (D), Undecided (U), Agreed (A) and Strongly Agreed (SA). Also, Yes or No options were used to seek opinions of respondents. The researcher also developed an in-depth interview guide to seek opinion of the respondents.

Ethically, data collected in the field was properly protected to avoid distortion and mislay of information. After sorting their consent, the study participants were assured that whatever they disclosed or admitted in the course of the interviews would be held in strict confidence. Also, they were given the freedom of expression and any information given was not under duress and their privacies were respected.

Data, Findings and Discussion

Table 1: Presentation of Quantitative Data based on identified Variables

Question/Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Are you aware of the incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis?	Yes	383	95.97
	No	13	3.27
	No Response	3	0.76
Total		397	100
Have you been using Keke to move within Uyo Metropolis?	Yes	370	93.20
	No	26	6.55
	No Response	1	0.25
Total		397	100
When last did you use Keke for public transport within Uyo Metropolis?	Everyday	296	74.56
	1-2 weeks ago	63	15.87
	21	21	5.29
	3 weeks ago	9	2.27
	1 month ago	2	0.50
	2-3 months ago	6	1.51
	No Response		
Total		397	100
What period of the day is most convenient for you to move with a Keke?	Morning	122	30.73
	Afternoon	70	17.63
	Evening	87	21.91
	Night	73	18.39
	Anytime	40	10.08
	No Response	5	1.26
Total		397	100
Keke riders have aided in the rising incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis?	Strongly Disagreed	2	0.50
	Disagreed	1	0.25
	Disagreed	3	0.76
	Undecided	132	33.25
	Agreed	259	65.24
	Strongly Agreed		

Total		397	100
Victims avoid reporting their ordeal because of embarrassment from relatives, friends, neighbours and colleagues	Strongly Disagreed	8	2.02
	Disagreed	7	1.76
	Disagreed	1	0.25
	Undecided	102	25.69
	Agreed	280	70.53
	Strongly Agreed		
Total		397	100
Both the rapist and victim do know each other at least by sight?	Strongly Disagreed	29	7.30
	Disagreed	40	10.08
	Disagreed	16	4.03
	Undecided	132	33.25
	Agreed	180	45.34
	Strongly Agreed		
Total		397	100

Source: Fieldwork (2019)

Table 1 show that majority of respondents constituting 385 representing 95.97 percent in affirmation said yes that they are aware of the incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis, 13 respondents representing 3.27 percent said that they are not aware of any incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis, while 3 respondents representing 0.76 percent neither accepted nor rejected the fact that they are aware of the incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis. However, majority of respondents in the study population are of the opinion that they are aware of the increasing

incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis. This popular opinion might not be far fetch from the truth.

Result also show that majority of 370 respondents representing 93.20 percent agreed that they have been using Keke to move within Uyo Metropolis, opinion of 26 respondents representing 6.55 percent is that they have not been using Keke to move within Uyo Metropolis, while 1 respondent representing 0.25 percent choose neither of the options.

When asking “when last did you use Keke for public transport within Uyo Metropolis?” majority of 296 respondents representing 74.56 percent said that they have been using Keke every day, 63 respondents representing 15.87 percent said that they have used Keke in the last 1 to 2 weeks, 21 respondents representing 5.29 percent said that they have used Keke in the last 3 weeks, 9 respondents representing 2.27 percent said that they have used Keke a month ago, 2 respondents representing 0.50 percent said that they have used Keke in the last 2 to 3 months, while 6 respondents representing 1.51 percent did not have any response to provide. They must have had their reasons.

Data shows that 122 respondents representing 30.73 percent said that it is convenient for them to move with Keke in the morning, 70 respondents representing 17.63 percent said that it is convenient for them to move with Keke in the afternoon, 87 respondents representing 21.91 percent said that it is convenient for them to move with Keke in the evening, 73 respondents representing 18.39 percent said that it is convenient for them to move with Keke in the night, 40 respondents representing 10.08 percent said that it is convenient for them to move with Keke at anytime of the day, while 5 respondents representing 1.26 percent did not have any response to provide.

Also, result show that majority of 259 respondents representing 65.24 percent strongly agreed that Keke riders have aided in the rising incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis, 132 respondents representing 33.25 percent said that they have agreed to this statement, 2 respondents representing 0.50 percent strongly disagreed, 1 respondent representing 0.25 percent disagreed, while 32 respondents representing 0.50 percent strongly choose undecided. This implies that Keke riders have aided in the rising incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis.

Majority of 280 respondents representing 70.53 percent strongly agreed that victims of rape avoid reporting their ordeal because of embarrassment from relatives, friends, neighbours and colleagues, a total of 102 respondents representing 25.69 percent agreed to the statement, 8 respondents representing 2.02 percent strongly disagreed to the statement, 7 to the statement respondents representing 2.02 percent disagreed, while 1 respondent representing 0.25 percent choose undecided.

Result also show that both the rapist and victim do know each other at least by sight. This is confirmed by the opinions of 180 respondents representing 45.34 percent who said that they have strongly agreed to this statement, 132 respondents representing 33.25 percent who said that they have agreed, 29 respondents representing 7.30 percent strongly disagreed, 40 respondents representing 10.08 percent disagreed, while 16 respondents representing 4.03 percent are undecided.

Presentation and Analysis of Qualitative Data gathered from In-depth Interview

What is your opinion Towards Keke Riders on the Incidence of Rape in Uyo Metropolis?

Mr. Ndianabasi Essien Tom (2019), a civil servant, residing at Nung Uyo Idoro said:

“It is not far-fetched from the truth that tricycle riders have involved in rape in Uyo metropolis. This is because at times when they discover that a particular victim does not have money to surrender to them, they might choose to rape the victim after being diverted to unknown destination or secluded area of target. Although, I do not know any victim of rape but information from reliable source revealed that there are cases of rape in Uyo metropolis and tricycle riders are the major players” (Personal Communication with Mr. Ndianabasi Essien on 6th June, 2019).

Apostle Uwem Friday Edemidiong (2019) in an interview said:
“I can’t really tell in this area of crime but if tricycle riders could be involved, I would say it is about 20% because even those that carryout the act of rape do not do it inside the keke. They always take advantage of young girls hawking in the streets, ladies and girls that are stranded and sometimes those found within secluded areas. Also, tricycle riders connive or conspire with rapists to rape their victims” (Personal Communication with Apostle Uwem Friday Edemidiong on 6th June, 2019).

Mr. Owoiboho Akpan (2019), a staff of Ubotex Nigeria Limited, Uyo said:

“Well, from the information I got from people, students who have been going for evening classes mostly those from far distances, have been victims of rape while on their way home. When they board a keke to their destinations not knowing that the occupants of the keke are rapists and the rapists will divert the victim to unknown destination and subsequently rape her. Some of them carry charms or cocaine to get any lady or girl of their choice easily” (Personal Communication with Mr. Owoiboho Akpan on 5th June, 2019).

Owoikemeke Justine Udoh (2019) a student in the Department of Communication Arts, University of Uyo, said:

“Tricycle riders have contributed to the incidence of rape. I know of two ladies who were raped after robbing them. One of victims was my church member as well as a nursing mother, though the rapists had sympathy for her since she was a nursing mother and the incidence took place along Abak road towards Ekom Iman Junction while the second victim was my course mate in the University who was raped to the point of being admitted in the hospital for treatment and the incidence took place at the extreme of Oron road, around Ifa Atai axis. Both of them attested to the fact that it all happened in the day time as a result of boarding tricycle” (Personal Communication with Owoikemeke Justine Udoh on 5th June, 2019).

CSP Francis Erhabor (2019), Divisional Police Officer (DPO), ‘D’ Division, Itam, Itu LGA in an interview said:

“We have few cases of rape involving tricycle riders. It is quite true that tricycle riders have participated in rape, though few are recorded. They divert their female passengers to places unknown to the victims and rape them at gun point. Sometimes, victims fell into their hands in the course of seeking for assistance or join in the discussion of introducing a business that seems to be captivating and more profitable than other kinds of businesses” (Personal Communication with CSP Francis Erhabor on 7th June, 2019).

Evidence from the study shows that tricycle riders have contributed heavily to the incidence of rape in Uyo Metropolis. It takes a tricycle rider nothing to pick any girl of his choice without any encumbrances and they offer fake promises to capture the attention of high minded girls with the motive to rape them.

Findings show that rape does not take place inside the Keke used in conveying victims; rather, it takes place either in the bush, uncompleted building, secluded environment and in few cases in the residence of the rapists. It was discovered that keeping late hours, indecent dressings among girls, unfavourable economic condition, free ride, have been the factors for increase in rape statistics, especially, in the city transportation.

This study has been supported by existing works of Jeremiah (2015), Olonade (2018) and Odey (2019). This finding reveals that tricycle riders are the ones who divert the victims to unknown destinations with a preconceived notion of what they will do to the victims. Rape is always an organized crime that involves people of similar mindset. The choice for rape can take place as an alternative choice mostly when they could not find a reasonable amount of money with the victim. Indecent dressings among female folk and keeping late hours were seen to be among the reasons for rape cases. Powerful drugs such as cocaine powder and other diabolical means were seen to be used by rapist once the victims board their tricycles.

Conclusion

Given analysis in the study, some conclusions can be drawn. The study aimed at investigating the incidence of rape involving tricycle riders in Uyo Metropolis. There is no doubt that tricycles are not only used for public transportation within Uyo Metropolis, but they are also notorious for being used for criminal activities including rape. Tricycle riders have been a great danger to the lives of their passengers and residents.

On the basis of the findings of the study, a positive correlation was found that tricycle riders have played a major role in the prevalence of rape in Uyo Metropolis either directly or indirectly and they have always been blamed for their involvement against innocent passengers. Indeed, victims of these crimes mostly passengers have lost their virginity, contracted infections and unwanted pregnancies causing emotional trauma to the victims.

In spite of the fact that the law enforcement agents are always on their patrol, some mounted surveillance at strategic locations within Uyo Metropolis to curtail tricycle related crimes, these efforts yielded little

result and as such, individuals have resorted to self-help. Rape is alarming mostly in the transportation routes across the constituent parts of Uyo Metropolis, hence, the following recommendations;

Recommendations

For this paper, the following recommendations were made;

- (a) The introduction of online booking tricycles for city transportation like Opay and many others are recommended because they are safe and secured for passengers and their luggage.
- (b) Passengers should be security conscious at all times mostly when boarding commercial tricycles. They should avoid keeping late hours, patronizing unbranded and untagged tricycles, distractions from phones, doziness, forgetfulness, difficult thinking, sitting in-between passengers, unnecessary bodily contacts and joining in the discussion of other passengers.
- (c) The law enforcement agents should be proactive in the discharge of their duties and activities of tricycle riders should be adequately monitored. The stop and search mechanism at strategic locations by the Nigeria Police should be given optimum support

and all tricycle riders and passengers should thoroughly checked once they are stopped.

(d) Informal policing structures should be adequately equipped through provision of funds, equipments and strong enabling laws that would guarantee their independent and unbiased discharge of their security functions. A concerted effort towards having a synergistic relationship between the formal and informal policing outfits in the state is recommended. This is particularly important due to the fact that the presence of this would ensure a complementary working relationship that would further improve on the efforts and progress made so far in terms of policing.

(e) Many victims of rape for fear of stigmatization and being blamed for their ordeal bear the pain of the crime committed against them, thereby leaving their assailants roaming free to perpetrate more crimes. It is recommended that victims of rape should report their ordeals to the law enforcement agents for further actions and for record purposes.

REFERENCES

- Akpor, A. (2009). Keke Marwa : The three-wheeler terror on the road. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2009/07/keke-marwa-the-three-wheeler-terror-on-the-road/> (Retrieved on 2nd January 2019).
- Balami, A. D. and Garba, S. (2019). Road traffic accidents, near-misses and their associated factors among commercial tricycle drivers in a Nigerian city. <https://irispublishers.com/abba/fulltext/road-traffic-accidents-near-misses-and-their-associated-factors-among-commercial-tricycle-drivers-in-a-nigerian-city.ID.000539.php> (Retrieved on 25th June 2019).
- Cohen, L. E. and Felson, M. (1979). Social Change and Crime Rate Trends: A Routine Activity Approach. *American Sociological Review*, 44, 588-608. In: Hesam Kamalipour, Mohsen Faizi, Gholamhossein Memarian. *Current Urban Studies*, 2 (2), July 1, 2014. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2094589> (Retrieved on 25th June 2019).
- Doyo, M. C. P. (2012). Tricycles and crime. <https://opinion.inquirer.net/40326/tricycles-and-crime> (Retrieved on 10th December, 2018).
- Galadima, B. (No date). Sociology of Crime and Delinquency II (Soc 303). University of Maiduguri centre for distance learning. Faculty of social sciences, Department of Sociology and Anthropology, University of Maiduguri.
- Idialu, B. (2016). Nigeria's tricycles of trauma. <https://nigerianobservernews.com/2016/12/nigerias-tricycles-of-trauma> (Retrieved on 4th October 2018).
- Isah, S. A. (2019) Tricycle operator was nabbed over rape of passenger in Abuja. <https://www.dailytrust.com.ng/tricycle-operator-nabbed->

- over-rape-of-passenger-in-abuja.html (Retrieved on 25th June 2019).
- Iwarimie-Jaja, D. (2012). *Criminology: the study of crime* (4thed.). Owerri: Springfield publishers Ltd, 646p.
- Laws of the Federation (1990). *Penal Code Act. Section 282 (2) and 283*. Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- Laws of the Federation (2003). *Child Rights Act. Section 282(2) and 283*. Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- Laws of the Federation (2004). *Criminal Code Act. Section 357 and 358*. Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- Laws of the Federation (2015). *Violence Against Persons (Prohibition Act). Section 1(1), Section 1(2) and Section 1(4)*. Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- Mgbemena, J. (2013). Language, communication on wheels and national development: the inscriptions on tricycle (Keke) example. *International Journal of English and Literature*, 4(10): 529-53. <https://academicjournals.org/journal/IJEL/article-full-text-pdf/20D379B41605> (Retrieved on 23rd March, 2019).
- Jeremiah, A. (2015). Tricycle operator drugged raped passenger. <https://www.legit.ng/495011-tricycle-operator-drugged-raped-passenger.html> (Retrieved on 2nd January 2019).
- Odey, P. (2019). Tricycle operator in police net for defiling 10-year-old girl in Akwa Ibom. <https://punchng.com/tricycle-operator-in-police-net-for-defiling-10-year-old-girl-in-aibom> (Retrieved on 31st March 2019).
- Okoli, A. and Alaribe, U. (2016). Abia enforces ban on street trading, reviews ban on tricycle operations.

- <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2016/08/abia-enforces-ban-street-trading-reviews-ban-tricycle-operations/> (Retrieved on 10th December 2018).
- Oladipo, O. O. (2012). The development and impact of motorcycles as means of commercial transportation in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(6), 23-239.
- Olonade, R. (2018). Nursing student dies after being raped by three Keke NAPEP drivers. <http://www.kemfilani.com> (Retrieved on 28th March 2019).
- Onuegbu, C. (2019). Rape, defilement: Akwa-Ibom receives over 180 cases, prosecutes 18 culprits. <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2019/12/rape-defilement-akwa-ibom-receives-over-180-cases-prosecutes-18-culprits/5th> December, 2019.
- Onifade, C. A., Aduradola, R. R. and Amao, S. O. (2012). The effect of socio-economic survival of commercial motorcycle/tricycle riders on African cultural values. *Global journal of human social science, arts and humanities*, 12(14), 45-52.
- Paradise News (2016). We rape countless women in Akwa-Ibom by hypnotizing them-Suspects. <https://paradiseneews.ng/897/we-rape-countless-women-in-akwa-ibom-by-hypnotizing-them-suspects> (Retrieved on April 2019).
- PM News (2018). Tricycle operator remanded over alleged rape of teenager. <https://www.pmnewsnigeria.com/2018/07/04/tricycle-operator-remanded-over-alleged-rape-of-teenager> (Retrieved on 5th July 2019).
- Reid, S. T. (1982). *Crime and criminology* (3rd ed.). In: Iwarimie-Jaja Darlington (2012). *Criminology: the study of crime* (4th ed.). Owerri: Springfield publishers Ltd, 646p

Scroll News (2016). Tricycle rider gave N200 after raping me, 15 years old victim. <https://issuu.com/newsscscroll/docs/e-newsscscroll-february-7-2016> (Retrieved on 31st March 2019).

Umaru, I. G. (2013). Commercial motorcycle activity, value creation and the environment in the developing world: the case of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science Research*, 1(1), 122–139. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/mth/ijssr8/v1y2013i1p122-139.html> (Retrieved on April 2019).

Yakubu, A. T. (2012). Determinants of earnings among commercial motorcycle operators in Kwara State, Nigeria. <https://www.omicsonline.org/open-access/determinants-of-earnings-among-commercial-motorcycle-operators-in-kwara-state-nigeria-.php?aid=17254> (Retrieved on 26th April 2019).